

APPLICATION OF MODERN INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN THE TRAINING OF CADETS IN MILITARY HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

Xabibulla Bekpulatov Bakhridinovich

Academy Of The Armed Forces Of The Republic Of Uzbekistan Head Of The
Special Faculty For Training Foreign Military Personnel, Uzbekistan
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7943358>

Annotation: The article deals with aspects of the introduction of information tools in the educational process of training cadets in a military university. The advantages of using information technology tools in conducting classes, as well as the methodology for using these tools in the process.

The article discusses the aspects of the introduction of information tools in the educational process of training cadets in a military university. The advantages of using information technology tools during classes, as well as the methodology of using these tools in the learning process.

Keywords: Educational process, information technology tools, cadet training, military university

Introduction to the information culture is not only the mastery of computer literacy, but also the acquisition of ethical, aesthetic and intellectual sensitivity. There is no doubt that cadets can master the ways of working with various electronic and computer innovations with enviable ease; at the same time, it is important that they do not become dependent on the computer, but appreciate and strive for lively, emotional human communication. Classes of cadets with a computer include four interrelated components: - active knowledge of the surrounding world; - phased assimilation of increasingly complex tasks and means of solving these problems; - changing the subject-sign environment on the monitor screen; - activating communication of the cadet with peers. The computer significantly expands the possibilities of presenting educational information, and makes it possible to increase the motivation of a serviceman. The use of multimedia technologies (color, graphics, sound, modern video equipment) allows you to simulate various situations and environments. Under the condition of the systematic use of electronic multimedia training programs in the educational process in combination with traditional teaching methods and pedagogical innovations, the effectiveness of training cadets with different levels of training is significantly increased. At the same time, there is a qualitative increase in the result of education due to the simultaneous impact of several technologies. The development of electronic multimedia tools opens up

fundamentally new didactic opportunities for the field of education. Thus, systems of interactive graphics and animation make it possible to control their content, shape, size, color and other parameters in the process of image analysis in order to achieve the greatest visibility. These and a number of other possibilities are still poorly understood by teachers, including the developers of electronic learning technologies, which does not allow full use of the educational potential of multimedia. The fact is that the use of multimedia in e-learning not only increases the speed of information transfer to students and increases the level of its understanding, but also contributes to the development of such important qualities as intuition, imaginative thinking. A multimedia product can contain no less information than a large museum or library. And since it is available to everyone, it must be organized in such a way that even a person who does not have a special education can understand it. When creating an educational multimedia textbook or reference book, developers face a number of difficult problems. Among them is the need to create a simple and intuitive interface that visually combines educational information with navigation tools; implementation of software tools for graphics and animation integrated with other multimedia tools; determination of the structural organization and form of presentation of educational material that correspond to the goals set. But in multimedia textbooks created by universities and institutes, especially in some special subjects, the focus is only on the content of the product, and not on the design and presentation of the material. To create a full-fledged educational multimedia product, it is necessary to solve a number of interrelated problems: software, design, the amount of graphic and textual information, structure and navigation, sound, animation and videos, interactive forms (search engine, training system). The use of computer technology makes it possible to make the lesson attractive and truly modern, to individualize learning, to objectively and timely monitor and summarize. The developmental effect depends on the design of the program, its accessibility for the cadet, compliance with his level of development and interest. Computer technologies make it possible to put before the cadet and help him solve various problems based on visibility (mediation). Today, information computer technologies can be considered as a new way of transferring knowledge that corresponds to a qualitatively new content of training and development. This method allows the cadet to study with interest, find sources of information, cultivate independence and responsibility in obtaining new knowledge, and develop the discipline of intellectual activity. The computer as a means of passive display of multimedia objects does not have a

fundamental novelty in didactic terms. Interactivity is fundamentally new for the field of education, thanks to which students can dynamically control their content, shape, size and color in the process of analyzing multimedia objects, view them from different angles, zoom in and out, stop and restart from anywhere, change lighting characteristics and perform other similar manipulations, achieving the greatest visibility. Consequently, the expediency of computerization of educational institutions is determined by the measure of achieving pedagogical, methodological and economic efficiency in comparison with traditional forms of educational work.

One of the most promising means of achieving learning objectives at the present stage is the development and implementation of computer training programs. Programs of this type are clearly focused on computer support for the process of obtaining information and forming knowledge in any area, consolidating skills and abilities, controlling or testing knowledge. The training program should ensure the implementation of the following pedagogical goals: demonstration of educational material; training in a specific area; testing and diagnostics in order to control the progress of the learning process; Actually, training. At the present stage of development of IT, software and hardware, the experience of using a PC in the educational process, it is advisable to accept the following classification according to functional characteristics: electronic textbooks - ET; laboratory workshops - LW; simulators - SIM; control programs - CP; catalog, databases for educational purposes - DBEP; subject-oriented environments (educational and specialized packages, modeling programs) - POS. An electronic textbook is a software and methodological complex that provides an opportunity to independently master a training course or any part of it. Electronic textbook combines the properties of a conventional textbook, reference book, problem book and laboratory practice. Laboratory practice. Programs of this type are used to make observations on objects, their relationships, or some of their properties; for processing the results of observations, their numerical and graphical representation; to study various aspects of the use of these objects in practice. Simulators serve to develop and consolidate technical skills in solving problems. They should provide information on the theory and methods of solving problems, training at various levels of independence, control and self-control. The PKST-2 shooting simulator available at the Armament and Shooting Department , which allows students to train the correctness and uniformity of aiming and firing from all types of small arms and grenade launchers. Thus, time is reduced, and most importantly,

material costs for the training of specialists at the department. Control programs are software designed to test (evaluate) the quality of knowledge. One of the most common forms of employment at military universities using IT is the creation of tests. The universal program "Test Constructor" allows you to use an unlimited number of topics, questions and answers, allows you to systematize knowledge and increase the accumulation of grades. Reference books, databases for educational purposes. Programs of this type are designed to store and present to the student a variety of educational information of an educational nature. These materials are characterized by a hierarchical organization and a quick search for information on various grounds or contexts. Currently, the system of military education is monitoring the creation of such databases for their use in independent work of students using interuniversity networks and the Internet. A subject-oriented environment is a training package that allows you to operate with objects of a certain class. The cadet operates with objects of the environment, guided by methodological instructions, in order to achieve the set didactic task, or conducts research, the goals and objectives of which are set by him independently. This type of program, in view of the training of low-level tactical specialists at military universities, is not typical, and has no practical application. The experience of developing and introducing information technologies into the educational process indicates that students are willing to work at a personal computer with training and control programs. Such classes cause real interest, make everyone work. At the same time, the quality of knowledge increases markedly. This indicates the prospects of their application. Currently, the active development of educational electronic environments and computer training programs is extremely relevant. The introduction of information technologies in the process of training military specialists at military universities will subsequently:

1. Fully conduct the entire course of study in a particular discipline on a computer (including lectures, practical exercises and control of mastering the material);
2. Save students from the procedure of searching and buying books;
3. Promptly edit the lecture material, taking into account new data that appear in a specific subject area, including through computer networks;
4. Improve the methods of presenting the material based on the analysis of the results of periodic testing of students on each topic;
5. Provide students with the opportunity to study lecture material and perform practical tasks at home.

Thus, the introduction of computer technologies can significantly improve the quality of education and facilitate the work of the teacher, thereby giving the opportunity to further improve the quality of knowledge and the following tasks are consistently solved: Determination of the need to use a computer. Determination of the degree of computerization of the educational process. Determination of the list of functions assigned to the computer. Development of a curriculum in accordance with the educational program.

References:

- [1] Bekpulatov X . B . Problems of ensuring information security in the training of future officer personnel and their solution //Educational Research in Universal Sciences 1, 71-75, 2023.
- [2] Rezyarov N. Развитие систем компьютерного моделирования в вооруженных силах США // Зарубежное военное обозрение. — 6, 17–23, 2007.
- [3] Bekpulatov X . B . Scientific and theoretical foundations of the use of information technology in improving the quality of education // European international journal of multidisciplinary research and management studies 1, 73-77, 2023.
- [4] Lyulkovich S.G. Тактическая подготовка слушателей и курсантов на базе компьютерного моделирования общевойскового боя: дисс. канд. воен. наук. — М., 158-160, 2003

